

Original Research Article

Flavonoid Glycosides From *Acacia Tortilis*

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Abstract

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From the leaves of *Acacia tortilis*, a new chalcone glycoside, 2',6'-dihydroxy chalcone-4'-O-glucoside along with the known compounds, vitexin and 4-methoxy chalcone have been isolated. The structure of compounds was identified by various spectrophotometric techniques (UV, IR, ¹HNMR, ¹³CNMR and Mass Spectrometry).

Keywords: *Acacia Tortilis*, Leguminosae. Leaves, Chalcone Glycoside, 2',6'-dihydroxy chalcone-4'-O-glucoside

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Acacia* comprising over 500 species is found in the warmer drier parts of the World, chiefly in Arab countries, Australia, Peninsula and Africa. In India, there are about 22 indigenous species, distributed throughout the plains. Some of the *Acacia* species are of considerable value for afforestation and reclamation of waste land. They are the good source for tannin, gum and timber. *A. tortilis* (Leguminosae) possesses valuable medicinal property and therapeutic potential so, it is also useful for treatment of various diseases like skin allergy, cough, inflammatory reaction and it is a plant well used medicinally by the local population where it is commercially found (Yadav et al., 2013). It is also used for the relaxation of smooth muscle. Earlier investigation from this plant reported the isolation of apigenin, quercetin, isorhamnetin glycosides, terpenes, luteolin and isoflavones from its leaves (Ilyas et al., 2003; Hasan et al., 2002). Medicinal properties and scanty work on this plant accelerates our interest to carry out its comprehensive investigation. We now report here the isolation and characterization of a new chalcone glycoside, 2',6'-dihydroxy chalcone-4'-O-glucoside along with the known compounds, vitexin and 4-methoxy chalcone from the leaves of *Acacia tortilis*.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The brown gummy mass obtained after evaporation of the methanol extract gave positive colour test for Flavonoids (Jung et al., 2006). TLC examination in toluene-ethylformate-formic acid (TEF 5:4:1) and benzene-pyridine-formic acid (BPF 36:9:5) systems showed it to be a mixture of several compounds. After several purification steps including silica gel column chromatography, three compounds were obtained, which were purified by repeated crystallization and labeled as (1), (2) and (3).

Compound (1)

Elution of the column with ethyl acetate-methanol (8:2-7:3) followed by crystallization with methanol-chloroform afforded pale yellow crystals (100 mg) m.p. 280-281°C. The elemental analysis agreed with the molecular formula C₂₁H₂₉O₉. It gave red colour with conc. H₂SO₄ and orange to red colour with aqueous NaOH suggesting it to be a chalcone (Kumar and Pandey, 2013; Shakila, 2016). Positive Molish test indicated it to be a chalcone

glycoside. The IR spectrum showed the characteristic bands at 2965 (br, chelated OH), 1684 (C=O) and 1462 (C=C) cm^{-1} . UV spectrum showed the absorptions at 365 nm (Band-I) and at 245 nm (Band-II). A red shift of 71 nm with $\text{AlCl}_3 / \text{HCl}$ in Band-I showed the presence of chelated-hydroxyl group (Ibraheim et al., 2011). Compound (1) gave greenish brown colour with alcoholic FeCl_3 , indicating the presence of 2' and 6' hydroxyl groups. The placement of hydroxyl groups at 2' and 6' positions was justified by its $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum which showed two exchangeable hydroxyl groups with D_2O by the off field signals at δ 13.6 (2'-OH) and at δ 12.85 (6'-OH).

Acetylation of the glycoside 1a with acetic anhydride and pyridine afforded an acetate 1b m.p 178°C. Its $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum indicated it to be a hexaacetate derivative as it exhibited the presence of six acetoxy groups (two aromatic and four aliphatic). A six protons singlet at δ 2.52 was ascribed to the aromatic acetoxy at 2' and 6'-position while the aliphatic acetoxy groups integrating for twelve protons appeared as a multiplet in the range of δ 1.78 to 2.05. A pair of meta coupled doublets at δ 6.24 ($J=2.0$ Hz) and δ 6.26 ($J=2.0$ Hz) were assigned to 3' and 5' protons of ring-A respectively. The ring-B protons (2,3,4,5,6) appeared as multiplet in the range of δ 6.77-6.85. A pair of doublets at δ 6.97 ($J=15$ Hz) and 7.85 ($J=15$ Hz) were accounted for α and β -protons of chalcone. The sugar protons appeared as multiplet in the range of 3.5-4.32 and 5.22-5.50, and one anomeric proton at δ 4.1 ($J=9$ Hz). The coupling constant supporting the β -linkage of glucose.

Compound (1) on hydrolysis with 6% HCl yielded a sugar and an aglycone. The sugar was identified as glucose by R_f value and co-chromatography with an authentic sample of glucose.

The UV and IR spectra of the aglycone and its derivatives showed that it contained a conjugated carbonyl group and three phenolic hydroxyl groups. It gave greenish brown colour with ferric chloride. The hydroxyl groups were placed at 2' and 6' positions of the chalcone as discussed above. The remaining hydroxyl group was placed at 4'-position since it gave a red colour with vanillin-HCl reagent and a red shift of 62 nm in band I with NaOMe in its UV spectrum (absent in glycoside) (Hillis and Urbach, 1958). Thus all the three hydroxyl groups were placed in ring-A with no substitution in ring-B (alkaline fusion of the aglycone gave benzoic acid). The presence of a free 4'-OH group in the aglycone, which was not found in the glycoside, indicated the sugar linkage in the chalcone at 4'-position.

The $^1\text{H-NMR}$ of the aglycone exhibited a pair of meta-coupled doublets at δ 6.20 ($J=2.0$ Hz) and δ 6.23 ($J=2.0$ Hz) for H-3' and H-5' protons respectively. The ring-B protons (H-2',3',4',5',6') appeared in the range of δ 6.75-6.82. It showed two signals for one proton doublet

each ($J=15$ Hz) for α and β protons and the $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ signal at δ 194.9 (C=O) of chalcone skeleton. Therefore, the aglycone was characterized as 2',4',6'-trihydroxychalcone (Jayaprakasam et al., 2001; Zhang et al., 2006).

The quantitative estimation of the sugar by Somogyi's copper-micro method (Sengupta et al., 2000). Showed the presence of 1 mole of glucose per mole of the aglycone.

The Mass spectrum (Scheme-I) of the glycoside 1a was in full agreement with the assigned structure of:

the glycoside. It showed the presence of glucose at m/z 180 and an aglycone at m/z 256. The retro-Diels-Alder fragmentation pattern was observed by peaks at m/z 152, 131, 126 and 104, supporting the presence of three hydroxyl groups in ring-A and no-hydroxyl group in ring-B. It was further confirmed by the degradation of the aglycone with 50% KOH which gave phloroglucinol and cinnamic acid which were identified by co-TLC with authentic samples (Anne et al., 2007). On the basis of the above results the compound (1) was thus characterized as 2',6'-dihydroxychalcone-4'-O-glucoside 1a which is being reported for the first time, and this was further supported by the analysis of its $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ spectrum.

The compounds (2) and (3) was characterized as vitexin (Darcy et al., 2007; Tayfun et al., 2002; Malikov and Yuldashe, 2002; Prox, 1968; Horowitz and Gentili, 1964) and 4-methoxy chalcone (Kumar and Pandey, 2013; Shakila, 2016; Ibraheim et al., 2011) respectively by comparison of IR, UV, $^1\text{H-NMR}$, $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ and Mass spectrums with that of authentic sample.

Experimental

Plant material

Leaves of *A. tortilis* were collected from Alwadeha, south of the kingdom of Saudi Arabia in the month of April. It

was identified by Prof. Wazahat Hussain, Department of Botany, A.M.U., Aligarh, India. The voucher specimen has been deposited at Department of Botany, A.M.U., Aligarh.

Extraction and isolation

The dried and powdered leaves of *A. tortilis* (3 kg) were exhaustively extracted with light petroleum ether (60-80), benzene and finally with methanol. The methanol extract was concentrated by heating over a boiling water bath, a brown gummy mass was obtained. It gave positive colour test for flavonoids. The examination in toluene-ethylformate-formic acid (TEF 5:4:1) and benzene-pyridine-formic acid (BPF 36:9:5) systems showed it to be mixture of several compounds. The brown gummy mass was purified by refluxing it with petroleum ether, benzene and chloroform. The semi-solid mass left behind was subjected to silica gel column chromatography. Fractional elution with benzene-ethyl acetate (1:1) and ethyl acetate-methanol (8:2-7:3) yielded three compounds. They were purified by repeated crystallization and labelled as (1), (2) and (3).

2',6'-dihydroxy chalcone-4'-O-glucoside 1a

Fractions obtained by the elution of the column with ethyl acetate-methanol (8:2-7:3) gave pale yellow solid. It was crystallized from methanol-chloroform as pale yellow crystals (160 mg), m.p. 280-281°C. (Found: C, 60.23; H, 5.20. C₂₁H₂₉O₉ requires C, 60.28; H, 5.26%). IR bands (KBr): 2965 (chelated OH), 1684 (C=O), 1462 (C=C) cm⁻¹. UV max (MeOH): 245, 278, 322 sh, 365; + NaOMe 244, 271, 324 sh, 366; + AlCl₃ 246, 284, 320 sh, 435; + AlCl₃/HCl 246, 282, 325 sh, 436; + NaOAc 245, 277, 324 sh, 366; + NaOAc/H₃BO₃ 245, 276, 323 sh, 365 nm. ¹H-NMR (300 MHz, DMSO): showed chemical shifts for one proton doublet at δ 6.24 (J=2.0 Hz, H-3'), one proton doublet at δ 6.26 (J=2.0 Hz, H-5'), five protons multiplet at δ 6.77-6.85 (H-2,3,4,5,6), one proton doublet at δ 6.97 (J=15 Hz, H-α), one proton doublet at δ 7.85 (J=15 Hz, H-β), sugar protons: one proton doublet at δ 4.1 (J=9 Hz, H-1"glu), four protons multiplet at δ 3.5-4.32 (H-1",2",3",4"), three protons multiplet at δ 5.22-5.50 (H-5",6"), one proton singlet at δ 13.60 (2'-OH), one proton singlet at δ 12.85 (6'-OH). ¹³C-NMR (150 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 126.4 (C-α), 144.6 (C-β), 194.9 (C=O), 129.4 (C-1), 132.6 (C-2), 131.7 (C-6), 160.1 (C-4), 115.0 (C-3), 115.0 (C-6), 114.5 (C-1'), 163.1 (C-2'), 95.9 (C-3'), 166.4 (C-4'), 99.7 (C-5'), 164.4 (C-6'), 101.1 (C-1"), 71.6 (C-2"), 74.6 (C-3"), 62.7 (C-4"), 77.8 (C-5"), 55.9 (C-6"). EI-MS (70 eV) m/z (%): M⁺ 418 (18), 256 (10.4), 238 (6.4), 228 (6.5), 104 (8.5), 103 (15), 152 (10.8), 179 (6.5), 131 (7.4), 91 (10), 126 (16.4), 55 (7.8), 54 (7.5), 78 (6), 180 (10.6).

Acetylation of 1a: Compound(1) (30 mg), was dissolved in pyridine (1 ml) and acetic anhydride (2 ml) was added. The mixture was heated on a water bath for about 3 hrs. After usual work up, as described earlier, the acetate obtained was crystallized from chloroform-methanol as fine needle shaped crystals (15 mg), m.p. 178°C. ¹H-NMR (200 MHz, CDCl₃): showed chemical shift for twelve protons multiplet at δ 1.78-2.05 (4 aliphatic acetoxy), six proton singlets at δ 2.52 (6H, s, aromatic acetoxy OAc-2',6'), one proton doublet at δ 6.24 (J=2.0 Hz, H-3'), one proton doublet at δ 6.26 (J=2.0 Hz, H-5'), five protons multiplet at δ 6.77-6.85 (H-2,3,4,5,6), one proton doublet at δ 6.97 (J=15 Hz, H-α), one proton doublet at δ 7.85 (J=15 Hz, H-β), one proton doublet at δ 4.1 (J=9 Hz, H-1" glu), four protons multiplet at δ 3.5-4.32 (H-1",2",3",4"), three protons multiplet at δ 5.22-5.50 (H-5",6").

Acid Hydrolysis of 1a: The glucoside 1a(60 mg) was hydrolysed by heating with 6% aqueous HCl on a water bath. The heating was continued for 2 hrs to ensure complete hydrolysis. The mixture was left overnight. The aglycone which settled down was filtered, washed with water and dried. It was crystallized with methanol-chloroform as yellow crystals yield (35 mg) m.p 176°C. ¹H-NMR (200 MHz, DMSO): showed chemical shift for one proton doublet at δ 6.20 (J=2.0 Hz, H-3'), one proton doublet at δ 6.23 (J=2.0 Hz, H-5'), five protons multiplet at δ 6.75-6.82 (H-2,3,4,5,6), one proton doublet at δ 6.95 (J=15 Hz, H-α), one proton doublet at δ 7.81 (J=15 Hz, H-β), one proton singlet at δ 13.0 (2'-OH), one proton singlet at δ 12.50 (2'-OH), one proton singlet at δ 10.1 (4'-OH). UV max (MeOH): 251, 298 sh, 368; + NaOMe 253, 280 sh, 319 sh, 346 sh, 430; + AlCl₃ 255, 321, 385 sh, 423; + AlCl₃/HCl 319 sh, 378 sh, 421; + NaOAc 282 sh, 341, 350 sh, 392; +NaOAc/H₃BO₃ 286, 353 sh, 381, 443 nm.

Acetylation of aglycone: Aglycone (12 mg) was acetylated by heating with pyridine (1 ml) and acetic anhydride (2 ml) over water bath for 3 hour. After usual work up it was crystallized with chloroform-methanol as white needles, m.p 155-56°C. ¹H-NMR (200 MHz, CDCl₃): showed chemical shift for six proton singlets at δ 2.45 (OAc-2',6'), two proton singlets at δ 2.34 (OAc-4'), one proton doublet at δ 6.22 (J=2.0 Hz, H-3'), one proton doublet at δ 6.25 (J=2.0 Hz, H-5'), five protons multiplet at δ 6.78-6.83 (H-2',3',4',5',6'), one proton doublet at δ 6.99 (J=16.0, H-β).

Degradation of aglycone: The aglycone (10 mg) was dissolved in 50% KOH (2 ml). The mixture was heated over water bath for 3 hrs. it was cooled and acidified by HCl. The solution was extracted with ether. And ether layer was washed with water to remove excess of HCl, then was shaken by NaHCO₃ solution, aqueous and organic layers were separated. The ether was dried by

passing over anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporated, the residue on co-TLC examination with an authentic sample of phloroglucinol showed it to be phloroglucinol. The aqueous layer was acidified by adding HCl and extracted with ether. The ether layer was washed with water and dried with sodium sulphate. The identity of the residue was checked by TLC and co-TLC with an authentic sample of cinnamic acid.

Identification of Sugar: The hydrolysate was concentrated and neutralized over KOH under vacuum and chromatographed on Whatman (No.1) filter paper using n-butanol-acetic acid-water (4:1:5 v/v/v) as the developing system, employing the descending technique. Authentic sugars were used as checks. The chromatogram was run for 24 hours, after developing, it was dried at room temperature and sprayed with aniline hydrogen phthalate solution heated at 100-5°C for 10 minutes. The sugar was identified as glucose (R_f 0.18) by comparison with authentic sugar (R_f , co-paper chromatography).

Estimation of Sugar: The anhydrous glucoside (30 mg) was hydrolysed by refluxing with 2% H_2SO_4 for 2 hours. After cooling over night, the aglycone was filtered and dried. The ratio of the aglycone to the glucoside was found to be (1:2) indicating the presence of 1 mole of sugar per mole of the aglycone.

Vitexin (2)

Compound (2) was crystallized from methanol-chloroform mixture as yellow needles m.p. 263-264°C (250 mg). It gave dark reddish-colour with Mg-HCl, and positive Molish test (2 ml of an aqueous solution of the compound was added two drops of a freshly prepared 20% alcoholic solution of α -naphthol). The mixture on treatment with 2 ml of conc. H_2SO_4 produced a red-violet ring which disappeared on the addition of an excess of alkali solution) and a dark brown colour with alcoholic $FeCl_3$ solution. (Found: C, 56.09; H, 4.62. $C_{21}H_{20}O_{10}$ requires: C, 56.12; H, 4.67%). IR bands (KBr): 3420(OH), 2950, 1650(C=O) cm^{-1} . UV max (MeOH): 268, 298, 335; + NaOMe 278, 325, 393; + $AlCl_3$ 279, 301, 353, 384; + $AlCl_3/HCl$ 276, 300, 351, 385; NaOAc 278, 300, 377; + NaOAc/ H_3BO_3 270, 308 sh, 342 nm. ^{13}C -NMR (300 MHz, DMSO- d_6): (C_2 164.0), (C_3 102.6), (C_4 181.9), (C_5 160.6), (C_6 98.9), (C_7 162.4) (C_8 104.2) (C_9 155.8), (C_{10} 104.2), (C_{11} 121.8), (C_{12} 128.5), (C_{13} 116.0), (C_{14} 160.9), (C_{15} 116.0), (C_{16} 128.5), (C_{17} 73.9), (C_{18} 71.4), (C_{19} 78.7), (C_{20} 69.9), (C_{21} 81.4), (C_{22} 16.5).

Acetylation of At-2: The crystalline glucoside (2) (30 mg), was dissolved in pyridine (1 ml) and acetic anhydride (2 ml) was added. The mixture was heated on a water bath for about 3 hrs. and then left overnight at room temperature. After usual work up, the solid obtained was crystallized from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether as

white crystals (At-5Ac), m.p. 154-56°C. (found: C, 57.79; H, 4.63. $C_{33}H_{32}O_{16}$ requires: C, 57.89; H, 4.67%). 1H -NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$): showed chemical shift for twelve protons multiplet at δ 1.72-2.02 (4 x OAc, aliphatic acetoxy), nine proton singlets at δ 2.32, 2.43, 2.51 (3 x OAc, aromatic acetoxy), seven protons multiplet at δ 3.65-5.70 (H-1", 2", 3", 4", 5", 6"), one proton doublet at δ 4.64 (J=10 Hz, H-1"), one proton singlet at δ 6.8 (H-3), one proton singlet at δ 6.91 (H-6), two proton doublets each at δ 7.4 (J=9 Hz, H-3', 5'), two proton doublets each at δ 8.1 (J=9 Hz, H-2', 6').

Hydroiodic acid oxidation: A mixture of the glycoside (2) (30 mg), phenol (70 mg) and hydroiodic acid (0.3 ml) was refluxed for about 9 hours. The mixture was cooled and sodium bisulphite ($NaHSO_3$) was added to it with stirring. The separated brown substance was purified by passing it through a silica gel column. Elution of the column with benzene-ethyl acetate (1:1) mixture afforded the substance, At-10agl. It was crystallized from chloroform-ethyl acetate as light yellow crystals. Yield (15 mg), m.p. 347-48°C. (Found: C, 66.64; H, 3.54. $C_{15}H_{10}O_5$ requires: C, 66.66; H, 3.70%). UV max (MeOH): 266, 297, 336; + NaOMe 277, 326, 395; + $AlCl_3$ 280, 303, 351, 382; + $AlCl_3/HCl$ 278, 300, 352, 384; + NaOAc 276, 300, 378; + NaOAc/ H_3BO_3 270, 306 sh, 345 nm.

Ferric chloride oxidation: The glycoside (2) (30 mg) was added to a solution of $FeCl_3$ (120 mg) in 3 ml water. The mixture was heated on an oil bath at 125°C for about 7 hours. The reaction mixture after cooling, was diluted with water (10 ml), a small amount of dark coloured solid formed was filtered off. The filtrate was purified by passing through a column of silica gel using water as eluant. The initial fractions obtained were combined and concentrated to a syrup which was subjected to paper chromatography on Whatman No. 1 filter sheet using n-BuOH-AcOH- H_2O (4:1:5) and n-BuOH-water-ethanol (60:25:8:16.5) as solvent systems and employing the descending technique. Authentic sugars were used as checks. The chromatograms were run for 24 hrs. and after drying at room temperature were sprayed with aniline phthalate and p-anisidine phosphate solutions. The chromatograms on drying at 100-105°C revealed the presence of glucose only.

GLC of Trimethyl silyl ether of sugar: The TMSi ether of sugar was prepared by taking 15 mg of sugar in dry pyridine (0.5 ml) and hexamethyl disilazane (0.2 ml) in a 10 ml round bottom flask. To this solution 0.2 ml of trimethyl chlorosilane was added. The flask was stoppered and kept at room temperature for one hour. The solution after drying was taken in heptane. The heptane soluble TMSi ether derivative of sugar was then subjected to glc (2% OV1, column temp. 150-250°C, 10 min. dect. temp. 300°, N_2 , 50 ml/min) along with the silyl derivative of standard sugar. The observed Rt. value was found to be in agreement with that of authentic sample

of glucose (Rt. glucose 1.0).

Periodate oxidation of glycoside methyl ether: Glycoside methyl ether (15 mg) of (2) was dissolved in methanol (10 ml) and an aqueous solution of NaIO_4 (0.47 N, 15 ml) was added to it. The mixture was kept at 20°C in dark for 24 hours. Solid NaHCO_3 (2 gm) was then added followed by the addition of Na_3AsO_3 solution (0.05 N, 25 ml). The resultant mixture was titrated against iodine using starch as indicator. One mole of methyl ether consumed 1.2 mole of periodate, with the liberation of one mole of formic acid.

4-methoxy chalcone (3)

Compound (3) was eluted from the column with benzene-ethyl acetate(1:1) mixture and crystallized with chloroform-methanol as light cream coloured crystals (165 mg), m.p. $77-80^\circ\text{C}$. The elemental analysis agreed with the molecular formula $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$. A red colour with cone. H_2SO_4 and orange to red colour with aq.NaOH suggested it to be a Chalcone (Kumar and Pandey, 2013; Shakila, 2016). (Found: C, 80.63; H, 5.85. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$ requires: C, 80.67; H, 5.88%). The IR spectrum displayed the characteristic bands at 1661 cm^{-1} (C=O) and 1475 cm^{-1} (C=C). Its UV spectrum showed the maximum absorption at 345 nm and minimum absorption at 245 nm . Analysis with the diagnostic shift reagents (Ibraheim et al., 2011) gave no shift in λ_{max} indicating the absence of free hydroxyl group/s in the chalcone nucleus, further supported by negative ferric chloride test.

The $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of Compound (3) showed a singlet of three protons at $\delta 3.87$ assigned to a methoxyl group. A pair of ortho coupled doublets at $\delta 6.92$ ($J=8.7\text{ Hz}$) and $\delta 7.59$ ($J=8.7\text{ Hz}$) integrating for two protons each were attributed to H-3,5 and H-2,6 protons respectively. Another pair of doublets at $\delta 7.39$ ($J=15.0\text{ Hz}$) and $\delta 7.76$ ($J=15.0\text{ Hz}$) were ascribed to α and β protons of chalcone. The 2',6' protons appeared as an ortho-coupled doublet at $\delta 7.99$ ($J=8.4\text{ Hz}$) while 3',4',5' protons were resonating as a multiplet in the range of $\delta 7.52-7.63$.

The above assigned structural data were further supported by the mass spectrum, which showed the molecular ion peak at m/z 238 (100). The fragment ions at m/z 161 (49.80) and 134 (15.15) supported the presence of p-methoxyphenyl ring. The other fragments: 239 (25.75), 223 (10.60), 210 (18.18), 133 (1.50), 105 (22.70), 78 (40.90), 77 (1.50). On the basis of above results, Compound (3) was characterized as 4-methoxy chalcone.

CONCLUSIONS

In the phytochemical studies of the *Acacia tortilis*, new chalcone glycoside, 2',6'-dihydroxy chalcone-4'-O-glucoside (1) were isolated from the leaves, along with Vitexin (2) and 4-methoxy chalcone (3). The structure of compounds have been briefly reported.

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(Scheme-I)